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An Early Account of Buddhist Ordination

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*Kiccho manussapaṭilābho kiccchaṃ maccāna jīvitam,
kiccchaṃ saddhammassavanam kiccho buddhānamuppādo.*¹

Hard to gain is birth as man; hard is the life of mortals; hard to get is the opportunity of hearing the *Ariya Dhamma* (teaching of the Buddha); hard it is for a Buddha to appear.

After getting enlightenment the Buddha started preaching his Dhammas for the welfare of the people. In this way, the Lord Buddha made his four-fold followers: *bhikkhu* (monks), *bhikkhunī* (nuns), *upāsaka* (laymen) and *upāsikā* (laywomen). Today, however, we have only Bhikkhu order (*Saṅgha*) and laity in India.

We all know that *Tapussa* and *Bhallika*, two merchants were the first in the world to become lay-disciples of the Buddha. These merchants bowed down in reverence at the feet of the Blessed One and thus addressed the Blessed One:

*“Ete mayam, bhante, bhagavantam saraṇam gacchāma
dhammam ca, upāsake no bhagavā dhāretu ajjatagge pānupete
saraṇam gate” ti.*²

(We take our refuge, Lord, in the Blessed One and in the Dhamma; may the Blessed One receive as disciples who, from this day forth while our life lasts, have taken their refuge in Him).

Further, the five ascetics (*Koṇḍañña*, *Vappa*, *Bhaddiya*, *Mahānāma* and *Assaji*) became the followers of the Buddha. With the proclamation of the Dhamma and the conversion of the five ascetics, the Deer Park (*Isipatanamigadāva*, Sarnath) became the birthplace of Buddha's *saṅgha* (community of monks). With joining *Yasa*, the son of a wealthy merchant (*seṭṭhi*) and his fifty four friends in the *saṅgha*, there were sixty disciples all together.

Their *Pabbajjā* (novice ordination or going forth) and *Upasampadā* (higher ordination) were granted by the Buddha in these words:

*“Ehi bhikkhū” ti bhagavā avoca- “Svākkhāto dhammo, cara brahmacariyaṃ sammā dukkhassa antakiriyaṃ” ti.*³

(Come monks, well proclaimed is the dhamma. Lead the Holy life for the complete cessation of suffering.)

The compassionate Buddha allowed his disciples to spread the dhamma in different parts of the country in following words:

*“Muttāhaṃ, bhikkhave, sabbapāsehi, ye dibbā ye ca mānusa. Tumhe pi, bhikkhave, muttā sabbapāsehi, ye dibbā ye ca mānusa. Caratha, bhikkhave, cārikaṃ bahujanahitāya bahujanasukhāya lokānukampāya atthāya hitāya sukhāya devamanussānaṃ. Mā ekena dve agamittha. Desetha, bhikkhave, dhammaṃ ādikalyāṇaṃ majjhekalyāṇaṃ pariyoṣānakalyāṇaṃ sātthaṃ sabyañjanaṃ kevalaparipuṇṇaṃ parisuddhaṃ brahmacariyaṃ pakāsetha. Santi bhavissanti dhammassa aññātāro. Ahampi, bhikkhave, yena Uruvelā senānigamo tenupasaṅkamissāmi dhammadesanāya” ti.*⁴

(I am delivered, O monks, from all fetters whether human or divine. You are also delivered from all fetters whether human or divine. Go now and wander for the welfare and happiness of Gods and men. Let not two of you go the same way. Preach the Dhamma (doctrine) which is excellent in the beginning, excellent in the middle, excellent in the end, possessed of meaning and the letter and utterly perfect. Proclaim a consummate, perfect, and pure life of holiness. There are beings who will understand the Dhamma. And I will go also to *Uruvelā*, to *Senānīgāma*, in order to preach the Dhamma).

The message of the Buddha attracted the people from different walks of life and showed their willingness to follow the Buddha and his teachings. Among them some wished to enter in the saṅgha. At that time, the monks brought these followers to the

Buddha for *Pabbajjā* and *Upasampadā* ordinations from various regions. The long journey tired both the monks and the seekers for pabbajjā and upasampadā ordinations. To avoid this hardship and inconvenience, the Buddha permitted the monks to confer the pabbajjā and upasampadā ordinations in any region. The process of these two ordinations were explained to the monks by the Buddha himself in the following way:

“Anujānāmi, bhikkhave, tumheva dāni tāsū tāsū disāsū tesū tesū janapadesū pabbājettha upasampādettha. Evaṃ ca pana, bhikkhave, pabbājetabbo upasampādetabbo - paṭhamam kesamassum ohārāpetvā, kāśāyāni vatthāni acchādāpetva, ekamsam uttarāsaṅgam kārāpetvā, bhikkhūnam pāde vandāpetvā, ukkuṭikam nisīdāpetvā, añjalim paggaṇhāpetvā, evaṃ vadehī ti vattabbo- Buddhāṃ saraṇam gacchāmi, Dhammāṃ saraṇam gacchāmi, Saṅgham saraṇam gacchāmi; dutiyampi Buddhāṃ saraṇam gacchāmi, dutiyampi Dhammāṃ saraṇam gacchāmi, dutiyampi Saṅgham saraṇam gacchāmi; tatiyampi Buddhāṃ saraṇam gacchāmi, tatiyampi Dhammāṃ saraṇam gacchāmi, tatiyampi Saṅgham saraṇam gacchāmi” ti.

“Anujānāmi, bhikkhave, imehi tīhi saraṇagamanehi pabbajjam upasampadam” ti.⁵

(Let him (who desires to receive the ordination), first have his hair and beard cut off; let him put on yellow robes, adjust his upper robe so as to cover one shoulder, salute the feet of the monks with his head, and sit down and squatting; then let him raise his hands and palms together and tell him to say:

“I take my refuge in the Buddha (the teacher), I take my refuge in the Dhamma (the teachings), I take my refuge in the saṅgha (the taught). And for the second time I take my refuge in the Buddha, and for the second time, I take my refuge in the Dhamma, and for the second time, I take my refuge in the saṅgha, and for the third time, I take my refuge in the Buddha, and for the third time, I take my refuge in the Dhamma, and for the third time, I take my refuge in the saṅgha”).

This was the process in which a follower gained pabbajjā and upasampadā ordinations in those early days. But with the passage of time, this short process had to be expanded by the Buddha himself as unsuitable and undesirable persons sought admission into the saṅgha. This process is still continuing in *Theravāda* ordination system.

Pabbajjā Ordination

In case of pabbajjā ordination, the follower has to recite the ten precepts in addition to the three refuges. These precepts (*Sikkhāpada* ⁶) are:

- | | |
|---|---|
| 1. Pāṇātipātā Veramaṇī | Abstinence from taking life |
| 2. Adinnādānā Veramaṇī | Abstinence from stealing |
| 3. Abrahmacariyā Veramaṇī | Abstinence from unchaste conduct |
| 4. Musāvādā Veramaṇī | Abstinence from false speech |
| 5. Surāmerayamajjappamāda-
-tṭhānā Veramaṇī | Abstinence from any state of indolence arising from the use of intoxicants |
| 6. Vikālabhojanā Veramaṇī | Abstinence from eating at the wrong hour |
| 7. Naccagītavāditavisūka-
dassanā Veramaṇī | Abstinence from dancing, singing, music and going to see entertainments |
| 8. Mālāgandhavilepana-
dhāraṇamaṇḍana-
vibhūsanatṭhānā Veramaṇī | Abstinence from wearing garlands, smartening with perfumes and beautifying with cosmetics |
| 9. Uccāsayanamahāsayanā
Veramaṇī | Abstinence from sleeping on a high or big bed |
| 10. Jātarūparajataṭṭigahaṇā
Veramaṇī | Abstinence from accepting gold and silver |
| Imāni dasasikkhāpadāni
samādiyāmi. | I undertake these ten rules of training. |

The ordination process for a *sāmaṇera* is finished here. The followers may not do this till he is at least eight years of age. After chanting these Pāli passages, the candidate becomes a *sāmaṇera*. If he wants to be ordained as a *bhikkhu*, should bow down himself three times and then takes the alms-bowl to the *Upajjhāya* (Preceptor). Then he puts down on his left side and having given the tray of offerings to the *Upajjhāya* bows down again three times and kneeling before the *Upajjhāya* with hands joined in the gesture of respect, chants the following passages for **Nissaya** (dependence) :

Ahaṃ, bhante,
nissayaṃ yācāmi.

Venerable Sir,
I beg for dependence.

Dutiyampi ahaṃ,
bhante, nissayaṃ yācāmi.

For the second time,
Venerable Sir, I beg for
dependence.

Tatīyampi ahaṃ,
bhante, nissayaṃ yācāmi.

For the third time,
Venerable Sir, I beg for
dependence.

Upajjhāyo me,
bhante, hohi. (three times)

May you be my Preceptor,
Venerable Sir.

When the *Upajjhāya* says either *Sāhu* (it is well), or *Lahu* (it is convenient), or *Opāyikaṃ* (it is suitable), or *Patirūpaṃ* (it is proper), or *Pāsādikena Sampādehi* (make an effort with blissfulness), the *sāmaṇera* should respond each time: *Sādhu, bhante* (Yes, Venerable Sir). Then the *sāmaṇera* says three times the following words:

Ajjatagge dāni Thero mayhaṃ ahampi therassa bhāro.
From this day onward the Thera's burden will be mine, I shall be the burden of the Thera.

Now the Upajjhāya tells the sāmaṇera that it is now time for the Saṅgha to ordain him as a bhikkhu in the Dhamma-Vinaya of the Buddha. In the Motion and Announcements the sāmaṇera's and the Upajjhāya's names will be mentioned. The Upajjhāya tells him his own name and the sāmaṇera's name and instructs him to tell them to the Ācariya when he is questioned in process of ordination. Also the names of the requisites for a bhikkhu, such as the bowl and robes, are to be memorized by the sāmaṇera.

Then the ācariya who is appointed to make the formal Announcement puts the sling of the bowl crosswise on the sāmaṇera's left shoulder in such a way that the bowl hangs behind the sāmaṇera. He then recites the name of the three robes, also of the alms-bowl. The sāmaṇera should reply as follows:

Ācariya : (touching the bowl)	This is your
Ayante patto.	alms-bowl.
Sāmaṇera : Āma, bhante.	Yes, Sir.
Ācariya : (touching the outer robe)	This is the outer
Ayaṃ saṅghāṭi.	robe.
Sāmaṇera : Āma, bhante.	Yes, Sir.
Ācariya : (touching the upper robe)	This is the upper
Ayaṃ uttarāsaṅgo.	robe.
Sāmaṇera : Āma, bhante.	Yes, Sir.
Ācariya : (touching the under robe)	This is the under
Ayaṃ antaravāsako.	robe.
Sāmaṇera: Āma, bhante.	Yes, Sir.

Then the ācariya will order the sāmaṇera to go to a prepared place with the words Gaccha amumhi okāse tiṭṭhāhi (Go to that place and stand there). At this the sāmaṇera will back away (on his knees) for some distance before going to the prepared place at least twelve cubits (six yards) away. This place is marked by a special piece of cloth laid there, intended as the ācariya's standing place. Behind this at a distance of a foot or two the sāmaṇera is to stand facing the assembled bhikkhus, hands joined in the gesture of respect. Care should be taken by the sāmaṇera to go round this cloth and not to tread or stand on it.

Upsampadā ordination

Informing the Saṅgha regarding the examination of the candidate

Now the ācariya, having paid homage to the Triple Gem by prostrating himself three times, in the kneeling position joins his hands in the gesture of respect and recites three times the preliminary passage revering the Buddha:

Namo Tassa Bhagavato Arahato Sammāsambuddhassa

Homage to the Exalted One, the Arahant, perfectly Enlightened by himself. He then sits in the polite sideways sitting posture and informs the Saṅgha that he will examine the candidate for bhikkhuhood.

Suṇātu me, bhante,
saṅgho.

Itthannāmo itthannāmassa
āyasmato Upasampadā-
pekkho.

Yadi saṅghassa
pattakallaṃ, Ahaṃ
itthannāmaṃ
anusāseyyanti. ⁷

Let the Saṅgha listen to me,
Venerable Sir.

This (name) wishes for the
Upasampadā from the
Venerable (name of
preceptor).

If there is the complete
preparedness of the Saṅgha,
I shall examine (name of the
candidate).

Examination of the candidate outside the saṅgha

Then the ācariya gets up and goes to the cloth spread for him. Standing on it, he examines the candidate as follows:

Suṇasi, itthannāma,
Ayaṃ te saccakālo
bhūtakālo.
Yaṃ jātaṃ taṃ
saṅghamajjhe pucchante

Listen, (name of candidate)
This is the time for the truth,
the time for what is factual.
Whatever has occurred,
that, in the midst of the

Santam atthīti
vattabban.
Asantam natthīti
vattabban.
Mā kho vitthāyi,
Mā kho mañku ahosi.
Evañ tam pucchissanti-
Santi te evarūpā ābādhā-

Kuṭṭham?
(candidate) Natthi, bhante.
Gaṇḍo?
(candidate): Natthi, bhante.
Kilāso?
(candidate): Natthi, bhante.
Soso?
(candidate): Natthi, bhante.
Apamāro?
(candidate): Natthi, bhante.
Manussosi?
(candidate): Āma, bhante.
Purisosi?
(candidate) : Āma, bhante.
Bhujissosi?
(candidate) : Āma, bhante.
Aṇaṇosi?
(candidate) : Āma, bhante.
Nasi Rājabhaṭo?

(candidate) : Āma, bhante.
Anuññātosī mātāpitūhi?

(candidate) : Āma, bhante.

Saṅgha, will be asked
Whatever is so, that
should be told.
Whatever is not so,
that should be told.
Do not be embarrassed!
Do not be confused!
They will ask you as follows:
Do you have diseases such as
these?
leprosy?
No, Sir.
ulceration?
No, Sir.
ringworm?
No, Sir.
consumption?
No, Sir.
epilepsy?
No, Sir.
Are you a human being?
yes, Sir.
Are you a man?
Yes, Sir.
Are you a free man?
Yes, Sir.
Are you without debt?
Yes, Sir.
Are you exempted from
military service
Yes, Sir.
Have you been permitted by
your mother and father?
Yes, sir.

Paripuṇṇavāsati vassosi?

Are you fully 20 years of age?

(candidate) : Āma, bhante.

Yes, sir.

Paripuṇṇam te pattacīvaram?

Have you the bowl and robes complete?

(candidate) : Āma, bhante.

Yes, sir.

Kim nāmosi?

What is your name?

(candidate) : Aham, bhante, nāma.

Venerable sir, I am named...

Ko nāma te upajjhāyo? ⁸

What is your Preceptor's name?

(candidate) : Upajjhāyo me, bhante āyasmā... nāma.

My Preceptor's name is Venerable... sir.

Informing the saṅgha that the candidate has been examined

Then the ācariya comes back before the assembly, prostrates himself once, sits in the sidewise sitting posture, joins hands and chants the following passages for calling the candidate :

Suṇātu me, bhante,
saṅgho.

Let the saṅgha listen to me, Venerable sir.

Itthannāmo itthannāmassa
āyasmato

(The candidate's name) wishes for the

Upasampadāpekkho.

Upasampadā from Venerable (the Preceptor's name).

Anusiṭṭho so mayā.

He has been examined by me

Yadi saṅghassa

If there is the complete

pattakallaṃ,

preparedness of the saṅgha

itthannāmo āgaccheyyāti. ⁹

let (candidate's name) come here.

The ācariya now turns to the candidate and calls him in by saying āgacchāhi (come here!). Then the candidate approaches the assembly and prostrates himself three times before his upajjhāya.

During his prostration, the ācariya or a bhikkhu nearest to him holds the bowl-strap to prevent the bowl from falling about. After this, the candidate kneeling down, utters the following passages asking that he shall be ordained.

Requesting the Upasampadā

Saṅghaṃ ,bhante,
 upasampadaṃ yācāmi.
 Ullumpatu maṃ, bhante,
 saṅho anukampaṃ
 upādāya.
 Dutiyampi, bhante,
 saṅghaṃ upasampadaṃ
 yācāmi. Ullumpatu maṃ,
 bhante, saṅho anukampaṃ
 upādāya.
 Tatiyampi, bhante,
 Saṅghaṃ upasampadaṃ
 yācāmi. Ullumpatu maṃ,
 bhante, saṅho anukampaṃ
 upādāyā ti.¹⁰

Venerable sir,
 I beg for Upasampadā.
 May the saṅgha raise me up
 out of compassion.

For the second time,
 Venerable sir,
 I beg for upasampadā.
 May the saṅgha raise me up
 out of compassion.

For the third time,
 Venerable sir,
 I beg for upasampadā.
 May the saṅgha raise me up
 out of compassion.

The Upajjhāya then informs the Saṅgha as follows:

Idāni kho, āvuso, ayam
 sāmaṇera nāma
 sāmaṇero mama
 Upasampadāpekkho.
 Upasampadaṃ
 ākaṅkhamāno
 saṅghaṃ yācati.
 Ahaṃ sabbamimam
 saṅghaṃ ajjhesāmi.
 Sādhu, āvuso, sabboyaṃ
 saṅho imaṃ

(candidate's Pāli name) Now
 Reverend Sirs, this
 named (name) wishes for
 upasampadā from me.
 Desiring upasampadā,
 he begs it
 from the saṅgha.
 I request all this from
 the saṅgha .
 Well, Revered sirs,
 when all the saṅgha, having

nāma sāmaṇeraṃ
antarāyike
dhamme pucchitvā, tattha

pattakallaṃ ñatvā
ñatticatutthena
kammena akuppena
ṭhānārahena
upasampādemāti kamma-
sanniṭṭhānaṃ karotu.

questioned this sāmaṇera
named (name) about,
the obstructing circumstances
and acknowledged
complete preparedness,
then we shall give
upasampadā by the Act
of Four (Announcements)
including the motion which
is firm and proper to the
occasion, bringing the Act to
a conclusion.

Examination of the candidate inside the Saṅgha

Then the Ācariya informs the Saṅgha of his duties as follows:

Suṇātu me, bhante,
saṅgho. Ayaṃ Itthannāmo
itthannāmassa āyasmato
upasampadāpekkho.
Yadi saṅghassa
pattakallaṃ,
ahaṃ itthannāmaṃ
antarāyike dhamme
puccheyyanti ?
Suṇasi, itthannāma,
ayaṃ te saccakālo,
bhūtakālo.
Yaṃ jātaṃ taṃ
pucchāmi.
Santaṃ atthīti
vattabbaṃ,
asantaṃ natthīti
vattabbaṃ.
Santi te evarūpā

Let the saṅgha listen to me,
Venerable sir. This (name) wishes
for upasampadā from the
Venerable (name of upajjhāya).
If there is the complete
preparedness of the saṅgha,
I shall ask (candidate's name)
about the obstructing
circumstances.
Listen, (candidate's name),
this is the time for the truth,
the time for what is factual.
Whatever has occurred, that
I ask you.
Whatever is so,
that should be told.
Whatever is not so,
that should be told.
Do you have diseases

After this, the process of questioning and answering between the ācariya and the candidate is carried on in the same manner as given above until the last question and answer :

ko nāma te Upajjhāyo?
Upajjhāyo me, bhante,
āyasmā... nāma.

What is your Preceptor's name ?
My Preceptor's name is
Venerable..., sir.

The Motion and the three Announcements

After the process of examination, the Ācariya chants the following Motion and Announcements to the Saṅgha :

Suṇātu me, bhante,
saṅgho.
Ayaṃ itthannāmo
itthannāmassa āyasmato
upasampadāpekkho,
parisuddho antarāyikehi
dhammehi,
paripuṇṇassa
pattacīvaraṃ.
Itthannāmo
saṅghaṃ upasampadaṃ
yācati itthannāmena
upajjhāyena.
Yadi saṅghassa
pattakallaṃ,
saṅgho itthannāmaṃ
upasampādeyya
itthannāmena
upajjhāyena.
Esā ñatti.

Let the saṅgha listen
to me, Venerable sir.
This (candidate's name) wishes for
upasampadā from Venerable
(Preceptor's name),
he is free of the obstructing
circumstances,
his bowl and robes
are complete.
(Candidate's name) begs
upasampadā from the saṅgha.
with Venerable (Preceptor's name)
as Preceptor.
If there is the complete preparedness
of the saṅgha
let the saṅgha give (candidate's
name) upasampadā with
Venerable (Preceptor's name)
as Preceptor.
This is the motion.

Suṇātu me, bhante,
 saṅgho.
 Ayaṃ itthannāmo
 itthannāmassa āyasmato
 upasampadāpekkho,
 parisuddho
 antarāyikehi
 dhammehi, paripuṇṇassa
 pattacīvarāṃ.
 Itthannāmo
 saṅghaṃ upasampadaṃ
 yācati itthannāmena
 upajjhāyena.
 Saṅgho itthannāmaṃ
 upasampādeti
 itthannāmena
 upajjhāyena.
 Yassāyasmato
 khamati itthannāmassa
 upasampadā
 itthannāmena
 upajjhāyena,
 so tuṇhassa;
 yassa nakkhamati,
 so bhāseyya.

Dutiyampi etamatthaṃ
 vadāmi-
 Suṇātu me, bhante,
 saṅgho.
 Ayaṃ itthannāmo
 itthannāmassa āyasmato
 upasampadāpekkho,
 parisuddho antarāyikehi
 dhammehi,

Let the saṅgha listen
 to me, Venerable Sir
 This (candidate's name) wishes
 for upasampadā from Venerable
 (Preceptor's name),
 he is free of the obstructing
 circumstances,
 his bowl and robes are
 complete.
 (Candidate's name) begs
 upasampadā from the saṅgha
 with Venerable (Preceptor's name)
 as Preceptor.
 The saṅgha is giving (name)
 upasampadā
 with Venerable (Preceptor's name)
 as Preceptor.
 If upasampadā is agreeable
 to the Venerable
 Ones of (candidate's name) with
 Venerable
 (Preceptor's name) as Preceptor
 let him be silent;
 he to whom it is not agreeable,
 he should speak.

A second time I speak
 about this matter.
 Let the saṅgha listen
 to me, Venerable Sir.
 This (candidate's name) wishes for
 upasampadā from Venerable
 (Preceptor's name),
 he is free of the obstructing
 circumstances,

paripuṇṇassa
pattacīvaraṃ.
Itthannāmo saṅghaṃ
upasampadaṃ
yācati itthannāmena
upajjhāyena.

Saṅgho itthannāmaṃ
upasampādeti
itthannāmena
upajjhāyena.

Yassāyasmato khamati
itthannāmassa upasampadā
itthannāmena upajjhāyena,
so tuṅhassa;

yassa nakkhamati,
so bhāseyya.

Tatīyampi etamatthaṃ
vadāmi -
Suṇātu me, bhante,
saṅgho.

Ayaṃ itthannāmo
itthannāmassa āyasmato
upasampadāpekkho,
parisuddho antarāyikehi
dhammehi,

paripuṇṇassa
pattacīvaraṃ.

his bowl and robes
are complete.
(Candidate's name) begs
upasampadā from the
saṅgha with Venerable
(Preceptor's name) as
Preceptor.

The saṅgha is giving
(candidate's name)
upasampadā with Venerable
(Preceptor's name) as
Preceptor.

If upasampadā is agreeable
to the Venerable Ones of
(candidate's name) with
Venerable(Preceptor's name)
as Preceptor, let him be
silent.

He to whom it is not
agreeable, he should speak.

A third time I speak
about this matter.
Let the saṅgha listen
to me, Venerable Sir.

This (candidate's name) wishes for
upasampadā from Venerable
(Preceptor's name).
He is free of the obstructing
circumstances.

His bowl and robes are
complete.

Itthannāmo saṅgham
upasampadam

yācati itthannāmena
upajjhāyena.

Saṅgho itthannāmam
upasampādeti
itthannāmena
upajjhāyena.

Yassāyasmato khamati
itthannāmassa upasampadā
itthannāmena
upajjhāyena,
so tuṅhassa;
yassa nakkhamati
so bhāseyya.

(Candidate's name) begs
upasampadā from the
saṅgha with Venerable
(Preceptor's name) as
Preceptor.

The saṅgha is giving (candidate's
name) upasampadā with
Venerable (Preceptor's name) as
Preceptor.

If upasampadā is agreeable to the
Venerable Ones of (candidate's
name) with Venerable
(Preceptor's name) as Preceptor,
let him be silent;
he to whom it is not agreeable,
he should speak.

Upasampanno saṅghena
itthannāmo itthannāmena
upajjhāyena.

By the saṅgha upasampadā has been
given to (candidate's name) with
Venerable (Preceptor's name) as
Preceptor.

Khamati saṅghassa,
tasmā tuṅhī,
evametam dhārayāmīti. ¹²

It is agreeable to the Saṅgha
therefore it is silent.
Thus do I hold it.

These four Announcements are to be made in full. The first Announcement is called the *ñatti* or motion, and the following three are called *anusāvanā* or information. Thus ordination is to be made by four complete announcements. The candidate having the state of *Upasampadā* has communion (*saṁvāsa*) with the Saṅgha from the conclusion of the ordination.

References :

1. Dhammapadapāli, pg.36, Vipassana research institute, Vol.47, Igatpuri, 1998

2. Mahāvaggapāli, pg.5, Vipassana research institute, Vol.89, Igatpuri
3. Ibid., pg.16
4. Ibid., pg. 24-25
5. Ibid., pg. 26
6. Khuddakapāṭhapāli, pg.2, Vipassana research institute, Vol.47, Igatpuri
7. Mahāvaggapāli, pg.120, Vipassana research institute, Vol.18, Igatpuri
8. Ibid.
9. Ibid.
10. Ibid. pg. 120
11. Ibid. pg. 120-121
12. Ibid. pg. 121-122